

Encephalitis and Acute Hemolysis Secondary to Paraneoplastic Syndrome From Renal Carcinoma: A Rare Presentation

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ABSTRACT

This case report details a 76-year-old man with stage 4 chronic kidney disease (CKD) who presented with altered mental status (AMS) and was subsequently diagnosed with encephalitis and hemolysis due to a paraneoplastic syndrome secondary to renal cell carcinoma (RCC). The patient's clinical course was complicated by acute chronic anemia, thrombocytopenia and left-sided kidney. Despite initial improvement after plasmapheresis and steroid treatment, the patient's condition worsened, prompting initiation of intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) for suspected paraneoplastic encephalitis. Multidisciplinary discussions led to a decision for comfort care due to poor prognosis and family preferences. This case highlights the diagnostic challenges and complexities in the management of paraneoplastic syndromes associated with RCC and emphasizes the value of an interdisciplinary approach and patient-centered care.

INTRODUCTION

Paraneoplastic syndromes (PNS) are rare disorders caused by the immune response to cancer and can present in a variety of ways, often mimicking other conditions. While paraneoplastic encephalitis is commonly associated with small cell lung cancer, it is rarely seen in renal cell carcinoma (RCC). Hemolysis and encephalitis, as part of the paraneoplastic syndrome in RCC, are extremely rare. This case illustrates the diagnostic complexity in identifying paraneoplastic encephalitis and hemolysis in a patient with advanced RCC, where early diagnosis and individualized treatment are critical to clinical outcomes.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 76-year-old man with a history of stage 4 CKD, hypertension, and a history of transient ischemic attack was admitted for AMS. His baseline renal function revealed an estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) of 20 mL/min/1.73 m². He had no history of malignancies or neurological disorders. The patient had no significant history of alcohol or drug use and no known family history of malignancy or autoimmune disorders.

CLINICAL COURSE

Day 1: Presentation The patient presented within two days with confusion, disorientation and lethargy. On admission, his vital signs were stable, but neurological examination revealed disorganized thought processes without focal deficits. Initial labs showed AKI on CKD, uremia, hyponatremia (sodium 160 mEq/L), and normocytic anemia (hemoglobin 9.2 g/dL). Brain imaging (CT and MRI) did not reveal any acute ischemic or hemorrhagic lesions. A lumbar puncture was performed, which showed normal opening pressure and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) with no signs of infection. Electroencephalography (EEG) ruled out seizure activity.

Day 3: Acute anemia and thrombocytopenia On the third day of admission, the patient developed worsening anemia (hemoglobin 7.8 g/dL) and thrombocytopenia (platelet count 42,000/ μ L). Laboratory tests showed intravascular hemolysis with elevated lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), reticulocytosis, low haptoglobin, and indirect hyperbilirubinemia. Due to the combination of hemolysis and thrombocytopenia, thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura (TTP) was considered.

Day 4: Initial treatment with plasmapheresis Plasmapheresis was initiated based on clinical suspicion of TTP, and the patient's mental status showed initial improvement. Steroids (methylprednisolone 1g IV daily) were also started. However, further testing revealed normal ADAMTS13 activity (>50%), ruling out TTP. Plasmapheresis was discontinued after two sessions due to lack of definitive evidence for TTP.

Day 6: Discovery of a renal mass An incidental finding on abdominal imaging revealed a large left-sided renal mass over 10 cm in size, suggestive of renal carcinoma. A multidisciplinary team including urology and oncology was consulted. Due to the improved mental state of the patient, an elective nephrectomy was planned after medical stabilization.

Day 10: Clinical deterioration and suspicion of paraneoplastic encephalitis The patient's condition worsened again with increased lethargy, dyspnea, and labored breathing, requiring BiPAP respiratory support. Neurology was again consulted and the working diagnosis shifted towards a paraneoplastic syndrome related to RCC, specifically paraneoplastic limbic encephalitis. Despite the absence of paraneoplastic antibodies in serum and CSF, the patient's symptoms were consistent with immune-mediated encephalitis. IVIG (2 g/kg for 5 days) was started and corticosteroids were switched to Decadron (12 mg/day) for better CNS penetration.

Family discussions and decisions about comfort care The patient's condition continued to deteriorate, respiratory and cognitive functions worsened. The oncology, nephrology, and pulmonology teams engaged in discussions with the family and presented options for aggressive treatment versus comfort care. Given the poor prognosis due to advanced RCC and the patient's deteriorating condition, the family chose hospice care with a preference for quality of life over further invasive interventions. The patient was transferred to comfort mode and died peacefully within a few days.

DISCUSSION

This case highlights the complexity of recognizing and treating paraneoplastic diseases, especially in patients with multiple comorbidities. Limbic encephalitis, an inflammatory process located in the structures of the limbic system (eg, thalamus, hypothalamus, amygdala, and hippocampus), is responsible for disturbances in behavior, motivation, emotion, and memory. Although limbic encephalitis is most often of paraneoplastic origin, it can also be strictly autoimmune-mediated without being associated with an underlying malignancy, the classic

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example being voltage-gated potassium channel (VGKC) antibody-mediated disease.^[1] In patients with limbic encephalitis, these manifestations often include acute changes in mood and behavior, hallucinations, short-term memory loss, cognitive dysfunction, and seizures.

Renal cell carcinoma (RCC) is not classically associated with paraneoplastic limbic encephalitis or other paraneoplastic neurological syndromes (PNS). However, cases associating RCC with PNS, including limbic encephalitis, have been rarely documented.^[2] Although most paraneoplastic neurological syndromes are associated with small cell lung cancer or ovarian and breast cancer,^[3] neurological syndromes caused by RCC are extremely rare. In fact, PNS such as encephalitis and hemolysis associated with RCC are rarely reported.^[4] Similar to our case, the literature suggests that early tumor detection and a multidisciplinary approach are key to optimizing patient outcomes.

Paraneoplastic syndromes, including encephalitis, are thought to be caused by an autoimmune response triggered by the presence of malignancy.^[5] This immune response often targets neurons, leading to neurological dysfunction. In this case, the incidental finding of a large renal mass combined with the patient's encephalitis and hemolysis raised the clinical suspicion of a paraneoplastic syndrome. An interdisciplinary approach – including oncology, pulmonology and nephrology teams – emphasizes the importance of individualized treatment plans in such complex situations.

Although plasmapheresis was initially considered for suspected thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura (TTP), normal ADAMTS13 activity excluded this diagnosis. The discovery of the renal mass shifted the diagnostic focus towards the paraneoplastic syndrome, which underlined the importance of excluding various differential diagnoses in patients with both hematological and neurological manifestations.^[6] Treatment options for paraneoplastic syndromes usually include treatment of the underlying malignancy, which in this case included consideration of nephrectomy. Due to the deteriorating condition of the patient and the family's decision for comfort care, the treatment was ultimately palliative.

CONCLUSION

This case presents a rare and complex presentation of a paraneoplastic syndrome in RCC presenting as encephalitis and acute hemolysis. It emphasizes the need for a multidisciplinary approach to diagnosis and treatment, as well as the importance of integrating patient and family preferences into care plans. Further research is needed to better understand the pathophysiology and optimal treatment strategies of paraneoplastic syndromes in RCC.^[7]

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